

Effect of architecture on the mechanical properties of self-reinforced composites

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Outline

- Manufacturing of commingled yarn based woven and knitted self-reinforced Polymer(srP) composites
- Optical microscopic image of srP composites
- Tensile response of srP composites
- Flexural strength of srP composites
- Comparison of srP composites with prosthetic socket material.
- Summary

Introduction

- The multitude of Self-reinforced polymers(srP) material's high mechanical properties and processibility embodies in different application like automotive, aerospace and construction industries.
- The commingled thermoplastic polymers enables manufacturing of composites at very short cycle times
- Prosthetic socket- An integral link which connects amputees residual limb to the rest of the prosthesis.
- Common materials: CFRP, GRRP, High-density polyethylene, polypropylene etc.

Objective:

- To perform mechanical characterization of the self-reinforced polyethylene terephthalate (srPET) and self-reinforced polylactic acid (srPLA) based thermoplastic composites.
- This commingled yarn based srPET and srPLA were examined in woven and architectural knitted preform to used as a candid material for socket manufacturing.

Manufacturing of srP Composite

- The fibre volume fraction of srPET is 49% and srPLA is 50%.
- Six layers of woven Twill 2/2 srP fabric were used to fabricate the laminate using vacuum-assisted consolidation.
- The low-temperature matrix fibre made to melt to act as a binder for the reinforcing fibres.
- 85% vacuum were maintained whilst heating at the rate of $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ until the consolidation temperature.

Laminate and optical Microscopy of srP woven composite

(a) The woven fabric and cured laminate of

srPLA

srPET

- The matrix is perfectly melted and encapsulated the reinforcing fibers in both srPET and srPLA laminates.
- No voids demonstrating the successful use of the thermal vacuum consolidation process of laminates

(b) The microscopic image of

srPLA

srPET

Architectural preforms of the srP composites

- The commingled thermoplastic yarn were weft-knitted with varying loop density.
- The architectural fabric of 400mm * 400mm were made using automated knitting machine.
- The similar vacuum-assisted consolidation were equipped for manufacturing PLA-K and PET-K laminate.

srPLA		srPET	
Case	Loop density($\frac{loops}{cm^2}$)	Case	Loop density($\frac{loops}{cm^2}$)
A (high)	21 (tight)	D (high)	20 (tight)
B (medium)	17 (medium)	E (medium)	16 (medium)
C (low)	13 (loose)	F (low)	9 (loose)

Tensile and flexural tests of srP composites

(a) Dog bone specime as per ASTM D638

(b) Flexural three-pont bending as per ASTM 3039

- The fabricated woven and knitted laminates were examined in both the direction.
- Tensile and flexural tests were performed at the rate of 1mm/min.

Tensile response of srPLA laminate

Table: The measured tensile properties of srPLA composite

Parameters	Ultimate strength (MPa)	Failure strain (%)	Elastic modulus (GPa)
PLAW-Warp	42±0.5	1.6	3.7±0.03
PLAW-Weft	41±2	1.8	3.85±0.25
PLA-high S.D(tight)*	36.65±0.73	0.014±0.0005	2.88±0.008
PLA-high S.D	33.94±1.95	0.014±0.0011	2.7±0.098
PLA-medium S.D*	34.85±0.73	0.0134±0.0005	2.97±0.09
PLA-medium S.D	31.82±1.06	0.0114±0.0005	2.96±0.12
PLA- low S.D(loose)*	26.44±1.38	0.007±0.0005	3.66±0.075
PLA-low S.D	23.90±3.34	0.008±0.0016	3.2±0.042

*- Wale direction; S.D- Stitch density

Tensile response of srPET laminate

Table : The measured tensile properties of srPET composite

Parameters	Ultimate strength (MPa)	Failure strain (%)	Elastic modulus (GPa)
PETW-Warp	127±4	19	4.45±0.25
PETW-Weft	132±5	19	4.35±0.05
PET-high S.D(tight)*	35.99±0.57	0.19±0.018	1.05±0.09
PET-high S.D	17±0.54	0.17±0.03	0.62±0.04
PET- medium S.D*	39.05±2.6	0.15±0.014	1.28±0.005
PET-medium S.D	13.02±0.73	0.11±0.015	0.338±0.02
PET-low S.D(loose)*	85.11±5.24	0.197±0.02	2.41±0.06
PET-low S.D	26.61±0.53	0.103±0.011	1.307±0.135

*- Wale direction; S.D- Stitch density

Flexural strength of woven and knitted srP composite

Comparison of tensile and flexural strength with the prosthetic socket materials

1. Phillips SL, Craelius W. Material properties of selected prosthetic laminates. *LWW*; 2005;17:27–32.
2. Campbell AI, Sexton S, Schaschke CJ, Kinsman H, McLaughlin B, Boyle M. Prosthetic limb sockets from plant-based composite materials. SAGE Publications Sage UK: London, England; 2012;36:181–9.
3. Odusote JK, Oyewo AT, Adebisi JA, Akande KA. Mechanical properties of banana pseudo stem fibre reinforced epoxy composite as a replacement for transtibial prosthetic socket. Association of Professional Engineers of Trinidad and Tobago; 2016

Summary

- In woven laminates
 - The Vacuum- assisted thermal curing of commingled yarn shows the matrix are well encapsulated with the fibres with less voids.
 - Tensile and flexural response of both srPLA and srPET provides relatively consistent properties in both the weft and warp directions.
- In knitted laminates
 - The properties of the knitted composite laminates were greatly influenced by the stitch density.
 - The srPET shows the anisotropic behaviour in material properties in which the ultimate tensile and flexural strength predominantly increases by decreasing the stitch density and increasing the loop length.
 - In case of srPLA, the properties exhibits the inverse effect by demonstrating minimal difference between the wale and course direction.
- The mechanical response of these srPET and srPLA offers good strength and ease of manufacturing with minimal time compared to standard resin infusion composite fabrication protocol.
- Employing automated 3-dimensional knitting technique to create the near-shape of the amputee's residual limb could emphasize realistic potential for producing customized patient specific sockets.